

Original Research

Association of Diabetic Retinopathy and Chronic Kidney Disease in patients with Diabetes Mellitus in a Tertiary care hospital of western Nepal

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Abstract

Background: Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) is a progressive dysfunction of the retinal vasculature caused by Diabetes Mellitus (DM), leading to structural damage to the neural retina. Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) is a progressive and irreversible condition characterized by a reduction in nephron number, ultimately resulting in end-stage renal disease, where patients become dependent on renal replacement therapy for survival. Retinal microvascular abnormalities are common in CKD due to shared pathophysiological mechanisms and can contribute to worsening vision through the progression of retinopathy.

Methods: A hospital-based cross-sectional observational study was conducted in the Department of Ophthalmology at Gandaki Medical College Teaching Hospital (GMCTH), Pokhara, Nepal, from September 1, 2021, to August 31, 2022, after obtaining ethical approval from the Institutional Review Committee of GMCTH (Reference Number: 174/079/080). A total of 84 patients with a known history of diabetes and chronic kidney disease, who were referred for retinal evaluation, were enrolled in the study. The collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using the SPSS, version 22. Data were presented as frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviations, and a p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: DR was seen in 90.5% patients with DM and different stages of CKD. The mean age of patients was 61.5 ± 11.11 years. 73.8% were male and 26.2% were female, 45.2% had DM for less than 10 years and 39.2% in between 10-20 years. There was clinically significant association between DR and CKD ($P < 0.001$) and between DR and duration of DM ($p < 0.002$).

Conclusion: This study found a high prevalence of diabetic retinopathy (DR) among patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) secondary to diabetes mellitus (DM)

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Diabetic Retinopathy, Renal Insufficiency, Chronic, Tertiary Care Centres

Introduction

Diabetic retinopathy is a microvascular complication of diabetes that damages the retina [1]. The prevalence of diabetes mellitus (DM) and chronic kidney disease (CKD) in Nepal is 8.5% and 10.6%, respectively [2,3]. The retinal microvasculature shares embryological and anatomical characteristics with the cerebral circulation; therefore, the detection of retinopathy can provide clues to the presence of underlying

cerebrovascular disease [4].

A delay in the diagnosis of retinopathy can significantly increase the risk of visual loss [5]. Screening and assessment of ocular status and complications associated with chronic kidney disease (CKD) are essential to prevent and manage irreversible visual loss, which can occur due to diabetes mellitus.

Since retinal microvascular abnormalities are common in chronic kidney disease (CKD), and diabetes mellitus accounts for more than half of all cases of renal failure, the presence of retinal changes may serve as a prognostic indicator of renal disease progression. This study was conducted to determine the association between diabetic retinopathy and CKD.

Materials and Methods

This hospital-based cross-sectional observational study was conducted in the Department of Ophthalmology at Gandaki Medical College Teaching Hospital (GMCTH), Pokhara, Nepal, from September 1, 2021, to August 31, 2022, after obtaining ethical approval from the Institutional Review Committee of GMCTH (Reference Number: 174/079/080). All patients who provided verbal consent and met the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. Patients with a history of diabetes mellitus and chronic kidney disease (CKD) were included. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire covering age, gender, habits (smoking, alcohol, or other substance use), symptoms, and duration of diabetes.

A detailed ocular examination was performed, including visual acuity, intraocular pressure measurement, anterior segment evaluation, and dilated posterior segment examination. In addition, blood sugar levels (fasting and postprandial), serum creatinine, and urine microalbumin levels were recorded on a predesigned proforma. The data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics were applied to calculate frequency, mean, and standard deviation with a 95% confidence interval. The Chi-square test was used to assess the association between different stages of CKD and the grading of retinopathy. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 84 patients with diabetes mellitus (DM) and varying stages of CKD were enrolled in the study. Diabetic retinopathy (DR) was observed in 90.5% of these patients. Among them, 73.8% were male and 26.2% were female. The mean age of the patients was 61.5 ± 11.1 years, with the majority belonging to the 5th and 6th decades of life. In this study, 39.3% of patients were younger than 50 years, 33.3% were between 50 and 60 years, and 27.4% were between 61 and 90 years (Table 1)

Table 1. Age distribution (n=84)

Age	Total	Percent
<50 years	33	39.3
50-60 years	28	33.3
61-90 years	23	27.4
Total	84	100

Out of 84 patients, 38 (45.2%) had diabetes mellitus (DM) for less than 10 years, 33 (39.3%) had DM for 10–20 years, and 13 (15.5%) had DM for more than 20 years (Table 2).

Table 2. Duration of Diabetes Mellitus

Duration of DM	Frequency	Percent
<10 years	38	45.2
10-20 years	33	39.3
>20 years	13	15.5
Total	84	100

The majority of patients, 29 (34.5%), had moderate NPDR, followed by 19 (22.6%) with severe NPDR, 17 (20.2%) with mild NPDR, and 11 (13.1%) with PDR, while 8 (9.5%) patients had no DR (Table 3)

Foreign bodies were most frequently lodged in the esophagus (52%).

Table 3. Stages of Diabetic Retinopathy

Stages of DR	Frequency	Percent
No NPDR	8	9.5
Mild NPDR	17	20.2
Moderate NPDR	29	34.5
Severe NPDR	19	22.6
Very Severe NPDR	0	0
PDR	11	13.1
Total	84	100

Of the 84 patients, 55 (65.4%) had stage V CKD, 13 (15.5%) had stage IV, 14 (16.7%) had stage III, and 2 (2.4%) had stage II. None of the patients were in stage I CKD (Table 4).

Table 4. Stages of CKD

Stages of CKD	Frequency	Percent
Stage I	0	0
Stage II	2	2.4
Stage III	14	16.7
Stage IV	13	15.5
Stage V	55	65.4
Total	84	100

Based on HbA1c levels, 46 (54.8%) patients had HbA1c ≥ 7 , while 38 (45.2%) had HbA1c < 7 (Figure 1)

Fig 1. Distribution on the basis of HbA1c

Patients were categorized based on urine microalbumin levels as mild (< 30 mg/g), moderate (30–300 mg/g), and severe (> 300 mg/g). Of the total, 24 (28.5%) had mild, 33 (39.2%) had moderate, and 27 (32.1%) had severe microalbuminuria (Figure 2).

Fig 2. Distribution on the basis of urine for microalbumin.

CKD was categorized into stages I to V, and diabetic retinopathy (DR) was classified as no DR, mild NPDR, moderate NPDR, severe NPDR, very severe NPDR, and PDR. The association between DR and CKD stages was analyzed among all 84 patients (Table 5).

Table 5. Association between DR and stage of CKD

Stage of DR	Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4	Stage 5	P value
NO NPDR	0	0	5	1	2	0.001
Mild NPDR	0	1	1	3	12	
Moderate NPDR	0	0	6	5	18	
Severe NPDR	0	0	1	3	15	
Very severe NPDR	0	0	0	0	0	
PDR	0	1	1	1	8	

Different stages of diabetic retinopathy (DR) were associated with varying levels of urine microalbumin based on the 24-hour urine microalbumin test (Table 6).

Table 6. Association between DR and urine for microalbumin

Urine Microalbumin	for <30 mg/24 hour	30-300mg/24 Hour	>300mg/24hour	P value
No NPDR	4	3	1	.000
Mild NPDR	10	5	2	
Moderate NPDR	9	11	9	
Severe NPDR	1	9	9	
Very severe NPDR	0	0	0	
PDR 0	0	5	6	

HbA1c levels were categorized as <7 and ≥7 to assess their association with different stages of diabetic retinopathy (Table 7).

Table 7. Association between DR and HbA1c

Stages of DR	<7	≥7	P value
No NPDR	3	3	0.049
Mild NPDR	11	7	
Moderate NPDR	13	18	
Severe NPDR	8	11	
Very severe NPDR	0	0	
PDR	3	7	

Most patients with moderate NPDR had a duration of diabetes of less than 10 years, while 12 patients had a duration of 10–20 years and 5 patients had a duration of more than 20 years. A statistically significant association was observed between the duration of diabetes and stages of DR ($p < 0.002$) (Table 8).

Table 8. Association between DR and duration of DM

Stage of DR	<10 years	10-20 years	>20 years	P value
No NPDR	4	1	1	0.002
Mild NPDR	9	8	1	
Moderate NPDR	14	12	5	
Severe NPDR	6	9	4	
Very severe NPDR	0	0	0	
PDR	5	3	2	

Discussions

Our study showed that the mean age of the patients was 61.55 ± 11.11 years, which is comparable to the findings of Thapa R et al. [6], who reported a higher prevalence of retinal disorders such as AMD, DR, and CRVO in the 40–60 years age group. Similarly, Pun CB et al. [7], in their study on the prevalence of diabetic retinopathy in a tertiary center in the western region, reported a mean age of 63.02 years. Schreur V et al. [8]. and Johnson L et al [9] also reported similar findings, emphasizing the importance of early diagnosis and treatment of preventable retinal diseases to reduce the risk of progression to chronic and vision-threatening conditions.

Bajracharya L et al. [10]. reported that the prevalence of CKD was higher among males than females, which is consistent with our study, where 73.81% of patients were male and 26.19% were female. This may be explained by the fact that kidney function in males tends to deteriorate more rapidly, often due to conditions such as glomerulonephritis, polycystic kidney disease, hypertensive changes, and diabetic kidney disease. Similar findings of male predominance in CKD patients were also reported by Chillo P et al. [11], Halle MP et al. [12], and Arogundade FA et al. [13]. In contrast, Tannor EK et al. [14] and Bao S et al. [15] observed a higher prevalence of CKD among women, suggesting that chronic renal failure (CRF) results in progressive deterioration of renal function that may be independent of gender [16].

Mahar P et al. [17] reported that the highest prevalence of diabetes mellitus (DM) was in the 41–50 years age group, followed by 30–40 years and 51–60 years, with the lowest prevalence in those above 60 years. In contrast, our study showed an increasing incidence of DM in the elderly population, which may be attributed to the lack of timely screening for chronic diseases such as diabetes and hypertension.

Pathak AH et al. [16], Hsing SC et al. [18], and Jitraknake J et al. [19] reported that diabetes mellitus was the most common cause of chronic renal failure (CRF), followed by hypertension. Similarly, Grunwald et al. [20] stated that in Western cohorts, diabetes contributed significantly to the development of retinopathy among CKD patients, which is consistent with our study. However, CW Wong et al. [21] found that retinopathy was independent of diabetes and hypertension, and instead was associated with progressive renal disease leading

to impaired kidney function, not directly related to elevated blood pressure or glucose levels.

In our study, the mean duration of diabetes was 12.30 ± 8.07 years, and the duration of diabetes was significantly associated with the development of DR. Nonetheless, DR may begin to develop as early as seven years before the diagnosis of type 2 diabetes, as demonstrated in studies by Maghbooli Z et al. [22] and Mishra SK et al. [23].

The prevalence of diabetic retinopathy (DR) among patients with DM and CKD in our study was 90.5%. Among them, 20.2% had mild NPDR, which is comparable to the findings of Shrestha A et al. [24], but higher than reports from neighbouring countries such as India (75%) and China, where prevalence varied across municipalities, with some reporting up to 100% [24]. In our study, the majority of patients (34.5%) had moderate NPDR, which is consistent with the findings of Pokhrel SM et al. [25], but in contrast to Rouf RSB et al. [26], who reported a prevalence of 68% for any form of DR among DM patients with CKD. The higher prevalence observed in our study may be explained by the fact that a larger proportion of patients (65.5%) had stage V CKD and were frequent visitors for dialysis. In our study, microalbuminuria associated with PDR was observed in 20.7% of patients and in 23.5% of patients with other forms of DR. Similar findings were reported by Cruickshanks et al. [27], Reddy et al. [28], and Padmaja et al. [29], where more than two-thirds of cases had microalbuminuria, and approximately half had proteinuria on routine urine examination along with abnormal urea and creatinine levels. These findings reflect impaired kidney function, which is considered an important risk factor for the rapid progression of DR. The Diabetes Control and Complications Trial (DCCT) [30] demonstrated a strong relationship between HbA1c levels and the development and progression of DR. Similarly, Lokesh S et al. [31] reported a lower frequency of DR among patients with lower HbA1c values, with the frequency increasing as HbA1c levels rose, which is consistent with the findings of our study.

Sabanayagam et al. [32] and Gao et al. [33] also reported that retinopathy was almost invariably present in patients with advanced CKD stages and was associated with more severe grades of retinopathy compared to those in CKD stages I–IV. Our study also found that the presence and severity of retinopathy were strongly associated with an increased risk of progression to stage V CKD and a reduction in estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR). However, this association was not statistically significant after adjustment for baseline eGFR and 24-hour proteinuria.

The increasing stages of CKD were associated with greater severity of DR, likely due to the shared pathogenesis of microvascular dysfunction in diabetic retinopathy and diabetic nephropathy. Both conditions are characterized by thickening of the basement membrane of micro vessels and increased vascular leakage, as explained by Pradeepa et al. [34] and Raman et al. [35], which is consistent with the findings of our study. We also observed that the risk of all-cause mortality was substantially higher among participants with CKD and those with DR. These findings suggest that regular screening of diabetic patients for both DR and CKD, along with close monitoring and timely management, may help reduce the risk of morbidity and all-cause mortality.

Conclusion

In our study, moderate NPDR was the most prevalent form of retinopathy, and the duration of diabetes mellitus was significantly associated with the severity of diabetic retinopathy. Given the high prevalence of DR among patients with diabetic CKD, regular fundus examinations, timely treatment, and close follow-up are essential to prevent blindness and visual impairment, thereby improving the quality of life in diabetic patients.

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